

IMPLICATION OF CLIMATIC CHANGE ON POULTRY PRODUCTION AMONG SMALL SCALE POULTRY FARMERS IN THE ZARIA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of climate change on poultry production among small-scale poultry farmers in the Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State. The specific objectives were the socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents and the implications of climatic change on poultry production in the study area. Community survey research was conducted using questionnaires administered to 100 respondents, and data were analyzed using descriptive statistical tools. The results showed that most of the respondents were married and were female in the study area. The majority of the respondents agreed that the high mortality rate in poultry, decreased feed consumption, decreased productivity, and heat stress are the major implications of climatic change on poultry production in the study area. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made. Proper housing systems should be put in place by poultry farmers to avoid overcrowding. Prompt veterinary services should be made available to poultry farmers to help them have access for proper treatment of their poultry birds. Extension service delivery systems should be promptly carried out by Subject Matter Specialists (SMS), and poultry farmers should always make water available to their birds when due.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is a major driver of national development by providing raw materials for industries, contributing to household and national income, and creating employment opportunities, particularly for small-scale farmers (Osai-Azubuiké *et al.*, 2023). Poultry production has long been recognized as one of the quickest ways for a rapid increase in protein supply, of recent there has been a recorded improvement in poultry production sub-sector in Nigeria with its share of the gross domestic product (GDP) increasing in absolute terms (Ayinde *et al.*, 2017).

Climate is an important factor in agricultural productivity. The threat of climate change to agriculture does not only apply to crop husbandry but also to livestock production and the general agricultural sector. Climate change has a negative effect on our environment and humanity, as is evident in the sharp decline of agricultural productivity. This has resulted in widespread hunger, malnutrition, and disease among farmers, as well as increasing poverty, particularly in Nigeria and across Africa (Damian and George, 2020).

Poultry birds can only tolerate mild changes in atmospheric and weather conditions, but the recent variations in climate and weather conditions have caused enormous fatality and high mortality rates in poultry production (World Bank Group, 2023). Studies have shown that the level of performance of birds depends on environmental conditions, such as rainfall, temperature, relative humidity, and prevailing sunshine. Housing systems, poultry house ventilation, and other management procedures have recently impacted poultry farming negatively (World Bank Group, 2023).

High temperature and humidity, for instance, increase the body temperature of poultry birds, decrease feed consumption and feed efficiency, and reduce body weight and size, whereas high and variant rainfall patterns cause a decrease in productivity and quality of eggs (Zhang, *et al.*, 2023). There are recent concerns that the ongoing global warming and climate change in Africa will have more negative impacts on the future growth and wellbeing of poultry birds.

Nigeria's water and wetland supplies have been impacted by climate fluctuations.

Many large water bodies are experiencing marked reductions in flow rate and network length in response to decreased rainfall and higher evapotranspiration. These have in turn impacted crop and animal productivity both directly and indirectly (Fitton *et al.*, 2019). Consequently, an increased risk of low output, crop loss, and livestock death is also expected. In animal production, the soaring temperature has affected productivity, especially in poultry, swine, cattle, sheep, and goats. Approximately 15% reduction in production has been reported per annum (Gbenga *et al.*, 2020).

Therefore, while the vulnerability to climate change impacts is higher in developing countries, including Nigeria, the readiness to improve resilience ranks very low in such countries (Okon *et al.*, 2021). A report by the World Bank, for example, shows that Nigeria is one of the top ten countries most exposed to the effects of climate change, with approximately 6% of its land area estimated to be exposed to extreme weather events (World Bank, 2019).

Climate variation results in high poultry mortality, reduction in poultry yield and nutritional quality of feeds, increasing disease and disease-spreading pests, reducing water availability, and making bird survival difficult. Climate variation manifests as a rise in temperature, increasing relative humidity, which provides a medium for fungal and bacterial growth. Disease outbreaks, such as coccidiosis, hemorrhagic syndrome, fowl pox, and bronchitis, will become inevitable. Changes in temperature reduce the rate of poultry feed intake, resulting in poorer performance (Akure, 2024).

Adereti *et al.* (2021) opined that climate change affects the rate at which poultry birds are affected by various diseases, his work further confirm that climate change affects the quality of eggs laid. Changes in temperature, relative humidity, and rainfall patterns cause the outbreak of poultry diseases (coccidiosis), resulting in a high death rate in poultry birds (Zhang *et al.*, 2023).

Damian and George (2020) highlighted that the impacts of climate change on our society are undeniable, as evidenced by desertification, rising flood levels, most notably in 2012 and again in 2022, and the occurrence of drought. All of these have in no small measure affected man, his animals, and crops. The threat of climate change has intensified, significantly impacting the Savanna region of northern Nigeria. This has led to a decline in socioeconomic activities, with the northeast and northwest being the most affected regions (Akande, 2017).

A study on climatic change implication on poultry production systems will serve as a useful tool in improving poultry production and serves as a guide for robust policy making. Therefore, there is a need for farmers to

understand climate change, have adequate knowledge of climate change, and have a good perception of its impact on poultry production, which can allow farmers to take necessary precautions in planning ahead to minimize loss or even use it for their own advantage.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in Zaria, which is located approximately within Latitude 11° 40' N and 11° 10' N of the Equator and Longitude 7° 38' E to 7° 46' 00' E of the Greenwich Meridian (Ejeh and Elisha, 2022). Zaria is the second-largest town in Kaduna State after Kaduna. It has a total land mass of approximately 61 Km² and is located at an average height of approximately 600 m above sea level, which is characterized by the metamorphic bedrock of the basement complex.

Zaria soils are leached tropical soils with ferruginous. The river system of the study area is dendritic in nature, and the major rivers found are Galma, Kubanni, Kamacha, Saye, Shika, and Yashi. Zaria has a population of approximately 408,198 people (2006 Census). The study area’s settlement pattern is mainly nucleated. Most of the population is engaged in agriculture, trading, civil service, and other jobs (Yusuf, 2013).

This study involved a community research survey design using well-structured questionnaires distributed randomly to 100 poultry farmers in the study area. Descriptive statistical tools, such as frequency distribution and percentage, were used to analyze the collected data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents

Gender: The results in Table 1 reveal that the majority (73 %) of the respondents were female, whereas 27 % were male in the study area. This showed that women are more likely to engage in small-scale poultry production in the study area than men.

Marital Status: most of the respondents (89%) in the study area were married, while 11% were single (Table 1). This implies that married people are more involved in poultry production than unmarried people to improve their income and standard of living.

Age: The results in Table 1 also revealed that 67 % of the respondents were between the ages of 26 and 35 years, while 10 % were below 26 years of age in the study area. This implies that most of the small-scale poultry farmers in the study area were between the ages of 26 and 35 years and were within their productive ages.

Educational qualification: The results in Table 1 show that 73 % of the respondents had secondary school certificates, while 8 % were graduates from tertiary institutions. This implies that the majority of the small-scale poultry farmers in the study area had a low level of education, which has implications for their low membership in cooperative societies related to poultry farming and access to information from the internet and other sources of information, such as extension services and veterinary services.

Major/primary occupation: The results in Table 1 show that the majority (77 %) of the respondents had farming as their major/primary occupation, with 10 % being civil servants in the study area.

Cooperative membership: Table 1 also indicates that 64 % of the poultry farmers in the study area are not members of cooperatives, whereas 36% are members of cooperative societies. This may be due to their low level of education and may affect their ability to obtain information on climate change from government and other non-governmental organizations.

Table 1: Respondents’ socio-economic characteristics

ITEMS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Gender		
Male	27	27
Female	73	73
Total	100	100

Marital status

Married	89	89
Single	11	11
Total	100	100

Age

Below 26	10	10
26-35	67	67
Above 35	23	23
Total	100	100

Highest Qualification

Primary school certificate (FSLC)	19	19
Senior Secondary School Certificate (SSCE)	73	73
Tertiary institution	08	08
Total	100	100

Major occupation

Farming	77	77
Civil service	10	10
Artisan	13	13
Total	100	100

Cooperative membership

Yes	64	64
No	36	36

Implications of Climatic Change on Poultry Production

The results in Table 2 reveal that the majority (100 %) of the respondents are of the opinion that high mortality rate, decreased feed consumption, decreased productivity, and heat stress are the major implications of climate change in poultry production in the study area. This is in consonance with the opinions of Gbenga *et al.* (2020), who revealed that heat stress increases the risk of low output and death of livestock. In animal production, the soaring temperature has affected productivity, especially in poultry, and has decreased feed consumption. Changes in temperature may eventually reduce the rate of poultry feed intake, decreasing production.

A large proportion of respondents also agreed that outbreak of disease and spreading pests (95 % strongly agreed, 5 % agreed), increase in poverty (93 % strongly agreed, 7 % agreed), decrease quality of eggs laid (91 % strongly agreed, 9 % agreed), loss of income (89 % strongly agreed, 11 % agreed), increase in temperature (88 % strongly agreed, 12 % agreed), increased water intake (87 % strongly agreed, 13% agreed), and poor poultry performance (81 % strongly agreed, 19 % agreed). This is in line with the work of Adereti *et al.* (2021), who opined that climate change increases the rate at which poultry birds are affected by various diseases. Their work further confirms that climate change affects the quality of eggs laid. Similarly, changes in temperature, relative humidity, and rainfall patterns increase the propensity of the outbreak of poultry diseases (coccidiosis), causing high death rate, loss of income, and increase in poverty among poultry farmers (Zhang *et al.*, 2023). Akure (2024) also reveals that disease outbreak becomes inevitable; thus, diseases like coccidiosis, hemorrhagic syndrome, fowl pox, and bronchitis will be on

the increase as a result of climate change. Similarly, the change in temperature also reduces the rate of poultry feed intake, resulting in poorer performance.

Table 1: Implications of climate change on poultry production

S / ITEM N		Strongly agreed	Agreed	Disagreed	Strongly disagreed
1.	High mortality rate in the poultry	100	00	00	00
2.	Increase in the temperature	88	12	00	00
3.	Decreased feed consumption	100	00	00	00
4.	Decreased productivity	100	00	00	00
5.	Disease outbreaks and spreading pests	95	05	00	00
6.	Poor poultry performance	81	19	00	00
7.	Decreased quality of laid eggs	91	09	00	00
8.	Heat stress	100	00	00	00
9.	Decrease in the water supply	51	22	18	09
10.	Reduction in the body weight and size	64	30	04	03
11.	Increase in the production cost	77	15	07	01
12.	Loss of income	89	11	00	00
13.	Changes in poultry performance	58	29	10	03
14.	Increased intake of water	87	13	00	00
15.	Increase in poverty	93	07	00	00

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the major findings of this study revealed that high mortality rate in poultry, decreased feed consumption, decreased productivity, and heat stress are the major implications of climatic change on poultry production among poultry farmers in the study area.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Poultry farmers should put in place proper housing systems to avoid overcrowding.
2. Prompt veterinary services should be made available to poultry farmers to help them have access to the proper treatment of their birds.
3. Appropriate and timely information should be made available to farmers through extension agents carried out by Subject Matter Specialists (SMS) promptly.
4. Poultry farmers should always make water available to their birds as at when to reduce heat stress.
5. Adequate provision of improved disease-resistant varieties of animals to the farmers should be accessible and provided at reasonable subsidized prices.

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